

ARCTIC PASSION

Deliverable 6.1

Instigate a new task group on
observations in the EU Polar Cluster

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**ARCTIC
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Key recommendations

To enhance the coordination of Arctic observations within the EU Polar Cluster and to improve the sustainability of the EU Polar Cluster the following five recommendations are proposed.

Recommendation #1: The EU Polar Cluster's newly developed online Observation Discussion Group/Hub should become operational.

Recommendation #2: Develop a mandatory questionnaire for EU Polar Cluster Members that provides the necessary meta-information regarding their Arctic observations.

Recommendation #3: EU Polar Cluster & ESA Polar Science Cluster to foster closer ties, especially regarding Arctic observations.

Recommendation #4: Develop a sustainable funding framework for the EU Polar Cluster.

Recommendation #5: Embed the coordination of the EU Polar Cluster within the structure of the newly formed European Polar Coordination Office.

By acting on these recommendations we (i) better understand the observations made by EU Polar Cluster Members; (ii) provide a forum to exchange information regarding each Cluster's observational and logistical needs; (iii) enhance cooperation between Members and organisations that can help with their observations; (iv) establish an accessible repository for knowledge and best practice regarding Arctic observations that the Cluster performs across disciplines, biospheres and cultures and (v) ensure the sustainability of the EU Polar Cluster.

1. Introduction

Given the global importance of the Arctic, combined with the rate of change occurring in the region, there has been an international push to better coordinate and link the numerous separately-funded programmes that are performed across the region each year. For Europe, the establishment of the EU Polar Cluster was a significant and positive step in this direction. The EU Polar Cluster, formally known as the Arctic Cluster, is a network of polar projects, funded by the European Commission, that encompass a broad spectrum of research and coordination activities (both Arctic and Antarctic) across all disciplines and sectors, including providing better access to polar infrastructure. Whilst the EU Polar Cluster involves EU funded programmes from both poles, this report focuses on the Arctic only¹.

A potential area where further work is needed, is the building of stronger links between EU Cluster programmes regarding the observations they perform and to better coordinate these observations along with their logistics. To address this challenge we need to:

- i. better understand the observations that are (were) being performed within EU funded Arctic programmes;
- ii. produce an accessible catalogue of meta-information of the EU Polar Cluster observations, contact points and information on when, where and how observational data are intended to be collected;
- iii. provide opportunities to connect with individuals and organisations that can assist the observational measurements and logistic needs of EU Polar Cluster projects by creating a forum/process that enhances the exchange of information regarding each project's observational and logistical needs.

Answers to these three challenges are presently lacking which begs the question, do we need an internal working group, or some other mechanism, within the EU Polar Cluster to better coordinate the observational measurements that are performed within EU funded projects?

Our document addresses these needs by (i) providing an overview of the key institutions involved in Arctic observations both within Europe and Internationally, (ii) introducing the EU Polar Cluster and role it plays in Arctic observations, (iii) summarising the outputs of a questionnaire and other knowledge gathering opportunities that provide information regarding the three challenges mentioned above, and finally (iv) synthesising the above information in order to provide a list

¹ This is because Arctic PASSION is an Arctic focused programme of research that aims to create an integrated Pan-Arctic observing system through local, regional and international collaboration.

of recommendations of how to deliver a stronger EU Polar Cluster that has more coherent links between their observational efforts.

2. European organisations involved in EU funded Arctic observations

Arctic research performed by EU funded programmes is carried out across all northern latitudes, seasons, disciplines, economic sectors and policy domains. These EU funded programmes generally run for between 3 to 5 years, and as such each year new programmes are initiated and active programmes are completed. Whilst the EU Polar Cluster can be viewed as an umbrella organisation that brings active EU funded programmes together, there is no single European organisation or institute that unites EU funded observations in the Arctic. There are however a number of key European organisations that play a leading role in Arctic observing, either directly or indirectly. We summarise the main ones below.

2.1 European Polar Board

The European Polar Board² (EPB) was established by the European Science Foundation in 1995, and since 2015 it has been an independent entity with its Secretariat hosted by the Dutch Research Council (NWO) in The Hague. From 2025 to 2029 the EPB will move to Umeå, Sweden. The EPB focuses on European strategic priorities in the Arctic and Antarctic research, promotes multilateral collaborative activities between Members, and provides a single contact point for the European Polar research community and for international partners. EPB Members include research institutes, logistics operators, funding agencies, scientific academies and government ministries from across Europe

EPB's vision:

- a strong and cohesive European Polar research community, wherein decisions affecting or affected by the Polar Regions are informed by independent, accurate, and timely advice from the EPB.

EPB's mission:

- to improve European coordination in Arctic and Antarctic research through improved information sharing, optimised infrastructure use and joint initiatives between Members.

² See <http://www.europeanpolarboard.org/>

2.2 EU-PolarNet and EU-PolarNet 2

Whilst not an organisation, but an EU-funded networking programme, EU-PolarNet and EU-PolarNet 2³ are mentioned because of the very successful role they have played in unifying Arctic (and Antarctic) research within Europe. EU-PolarNet, and its subsequent follow-on project EU-PolarNet 2, are the world's largest consortium of expertise and infrastructure for polar research. The first EU-PolarNet began in 2015 and ran until 2020. It involved 17 countries which represented 22 of Europe's polar research institutions. The next phase, EU-PolarNet 2, commenced at the completion of EU-PolarNet in 2020, and runs until the end of 2024. Like its predecessor, it is the world's largest consortium of polar research expertise and infrastructures and is composed of 25 partners representing all European Member States and Associated Countries which have well-established polar programmes.

Over the years the EU-PolarNet and EU-PolarNet 2 have actively developed and delivered a strategic framework and mechanisms to prioritise polar science, optimise the use of polar infrastructure, and broker new partnerships that have led to the co-design of high-impact polar research projects. These results have shown to deliver tangible benefits for the region (Arctic), Europe and global society. To ensure this level of output EU-PolarNet and EU-PolarNet 2 have sustained and fostered interaction and coordination with the European polar research community and operators. By doing so they have engaged in closer cooperation with relevant actors on a national and international level.

Being a key European polar network, both EU-PolarNet and EU-PolarNet 2 have worked closely with the European Polar Board (EPB), and thus outcomes from EU-PolarNet and EU-PolarNet 2 add long-term value to EPB activities, as well as providing strategic science policy advice to the European Commission and other international bodies. EU-PolarNet 2 will finish at the end of 2024 and cannot be renewed a third time. To ensure such an important platform for European and International collaboration in polar science is sustained, a permanent European Polar Coordination Office (EPCO), which continues the philosophy and activities of EU-PolarNet and EU-PolarNet 2, will be established at the EPB.

2.2.1 European Polar Coordination Office

As a legacy of EU-PolarNet 2, the EPB will host the European Polar Coordination Office (EPCO) from January 2025. The EPCO will serve as a single contact point between the European science community and the European Commission (EC) as

³ See <https://www.eu-polarnet.eu/>

well as with policy/decision makers and other relevant stakeholders. The EPCO will represent EU funded polar projects and broadly, European researchers working in the polar regions. This will enable European policy actors, like the EC, or national, regional and international agencies to gain access to expert input and advice. By doing so, an informed and evidence-based decision-making process on polar issues, opportunities, priorities and challenges can be made.

EPCO aims to raise awareness of the importance of the polar regions in the global climate systems, aiming to ensure funding for polar research is available in EU and other funding agencies by open and competitive funding calls. The EPCO will facilitate collaboration and cooperation within the European polar science community, and it is possible that it will coordinate the EU Polar Cluster.

2.3 Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System

The Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System⁴ (SIOS) is an international observing system for long-term measurements that addresses Earth System Science questions on and around the Norwegian archipelago of Svalbard. There are about two-dozen partners from Europe and Asia that participate in SIOS. Their objective is to establish better coordinated services for the International Research community with respect to access, data and knowledge management, logistics and training. SIOS brings observations together into a coherent, integrated and sustainable observational programme. Within SIOS, researchers can cooperate to access instruments, acquire data and address questions that would not be practical or cost effective for a single institution or nation alone. SIOS integrates the existing distributed observational infrastructure and generates added value for all partners beyond what their individual capacities can provide.

SIOS' vision

- To be the leading long-term observing system in the Arctic to serve Earth system science and society.

SIOS' mission

- Develop an efficient observing system.
- Share technology, experience and data.
- Close knowledge gaps.
- Decrease the environmental footprint of science.

⁴ See <https://sios-svalbard.org/>

2.4 European Global Ocean Observing System

In contrast to EPB, EU-PolarNet, EU-PolarNet 2 and SIOS, the European Global Ocean Observing System⁵ (EuroGOOS) is focused solely on the ocean. EuroGOOS identifies priorities, enhances cooperation and promotes the benefits of operational oceanography. By doing so it ensures sustained observations are performed in Europe's seas, which in turn underpin a suite of products and services for marine and maritime users. EuroGOOS is an association of national governmental agencies, research organisations, and private companies, committed to oceanography within the context of the intergovernmental Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS). EuroGOOS is one of the UNESCO-IOC Global Ocean Observing System regions. Founded in 1994, with its headquarters are in Brussels, EuroGOOS has 48 members from 19 European countries providing operational oceanographic services and carrying out marine research.

The goals of EuroGOOS are to identify strategies, cooperate, co-produce, and promote the operational oceanography value for society. All EuroGOOS activities are developed within the framework of the European Ocean Observing System (EOOS) which sets out a vision for a truly integrated end-to-end ocean observing in Europe, for the benefit of society, science and innovation.

2.5 International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic

The International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic⁶ (INTERACT) is a long running, EU funded, Arctic network of 74 terrestrial field bases (as of 2024), with an additional 21 research stations in Russia on pause. The bases are located in northern Europe, US, Canada, Greenland, Iceland, the Faroe Islands and Scotland, as well as stations in northern alpine areas. INTERACT specifically seeks to build capacity for research and monitoring all over the Arctic by offering access to numerous research stations. The main objective of INTERACT is to build capacity for identifying, understanding, predicting and responding to diverse environmental changes throughout the wide environmental and land-use envelopes of the Arctic. This is necessary because the Arctic is so vast and so sparsely populated that environmental observing capacity is limited compared to most other latitudes.

⁵ See <https://eurogoos.eu/>

⁶ See <https://eu-interact.org/>

2.6 New European additions to Arctic Observations

2.6.1 The Copernicus Arctic Hub

The Copernicus Arctic Hub⁷ is a new development from the Commission that aims to provide access to data and information on the Arctic. When completed, it will provide open and free Earth Observation data in the Arctic region from the Copernicus Sentinel satellites and all Copernicus Services (marine, land, atmosphere, climate, emergency). This includes air, sea and land products and information that describes the Arctic environment in the context of climate change.

2.6.2 European Space Agency Polar science Cluster

The European Space Agency (ESA) Polar Science Cluster⁸ is a relatively new initiative that contributes and promotes networking, collaborative research, and fostering international collaboration. It involves different ESA funded polar projects and activities bringing together different expertise, data and resources in a synergistic manner. With this approach ESA aims to establish a stronger European Polar research area in close collaboration with the European Commission (EC) Directorate General for Research and Innovation and other European and International partners.

Presently, both the EC and ESA are strengthening their collaborations. A good example is the combined EC and ESA “European Polar Science Week” held in 2022. Furthermore, ESA had an Invitation to Tender which includes collaboration with the ESA and EC projects. The results of this tender are not currently known.

2.6.3 PolarDEX

PolarDEX⁹ is a newly developed operational tool for polar scientists and planners. The platform lists key polar infrastructures in both the Arctic and the Antarctic, enabling logistics discovery and enhanced planning opportunities. PolarDEX has been developed by the EPB through the EPB's Action Group on Infrastructure, in close cooperation in close collaboration with, and data provision by, SOOS, SIOS, INTERACT, IAATO, EU-PolarNet 2, COMNAP, Isaaffik, ARICE, EUROFLEETS, AWI and BAS. The PolarDEX platform was developed by Blue Lobster IT Ltd.

⁷ See <https://www.arctic.hub.copernicus.eu/>

⁸ See <https://eo4society.esa.int/communities/scientists/esa-polar-science-cluster/>

⁹ See <https://polarDEX.org/>

3. The role of the EU Polar Cluster in Arctic Observations

The EU Polar Cluster¹⁰ (previously known as the Arctic Cluster) is a network of collaborative polar projects which are funded by the European Commission. Besides these projects the EU Polar Cluster has four permanent members: (i) the EPB, (ii) SIOS, (iii) APECS, and (iv) EuroGOOS.

The objective of the EU Polar Cluster is to bring insights from the various areas of expertise together to provide one entry point to EU funded Polar research. Jointly, they aim to provide policy-relevant information to support the EU in implementing its integrated policy for the Arctic. The EU Polar Cluster is presently (as of 2024) coordinated by three entities (i) EU-PolarNet 2, (ii) EPB and (iii) the British Antarctic Survey (BAS). EU Polar Cluster has a range of Arctic, Antarctic and Southern Ocean, and Polar projects. As of 2024 active projects¹¹ included:

- Arctic: ACCIBERG, AI-ARC, Arctic PASSION, ArcticHubs, CHARTER, ECOTIP, EPOC, EuroGOOS/Arctic ROOS, FACE-IT, HiAOOS, ICEBERG, ILLUQ, INTERACT, SIOS
- Antarctic/Southern Ocean: Beyond EPICA, SO-CHIC, TiPACCs
- Both poles: CERTAINTY, CRiceS, EU-PolarNet 2, OCEAN:ICE, POLARIN, PolarRES, PROTECT, SEA-Quester

The EU Polar Cluster covers a wide spectrum of research and coordination activities, ranging from the most up-to-date findings on permafrost and sea ice, through to enhancing observations, improving predictions, networking research stations and coordinating access to icebreakers. Arctic observations performed by EU Cluster projects cover a broad range of mediums (air, ocean, terrestrial, cryosphere, and atmosphere), as well the covering the ecosystems and the human dimension (including policy).

The EU Polar Cluster has grown sustainably over the years, and with this growth there has been an increase in the range of activities performed by the Cluster. Because of this, Members are more integrated and knowledgeable regarding the aims and objectives of each Cluster project. For example, through the hard work of the coordination team many EU Polar Cluster Members work together on complementary topics, such as producing policy briefings that can achieve a larger and more diverse impact.

The future of the EU Polar Cluster is far from guaranteed, as the funding comes from only 3 of the over 20 presently active cluster projects. The three being EU-PolarNet

¹⁰ See <https://www.polarcluster.eu/>

¹¹ It is important to note that there are mechanisms whereby EU Polar Cluster projects that have been completed can continue to provide valuable input to the Cluster.

2, Arctic PASSION and OCEAN:ICE. One option being explored to improve this situation is for the EPB, via the hosting of the EPCO, to incorporate the coordination of the EU Polar Cluster.

The EU Polar Cluster has several working groups and action groups that create smaller networks within the EU Polar Cluster that are focussed on specific topics. But none are focused on observations at present. In addition the Cluster manages the Catalyst platform¹², a forum site for Cluster Members to open discussions and share resources.

In order to establish if there is a need for the EU Polar Cluster to play a more proactive role in observational efforts made by Cluster members we organised information gathering exercises through a questionnaire, the EU Polar Cluster Booth and sessions at conferences. We explain each in the next section.

Note: it is not the aim of this deliverable to duplicate or overlap with already active teams. For example the Data Management Working Group which covers (open) access to data, data standards and parameters. Also EU PolatNet2 have recently produced a White paper with recommendations to accelerate the development of a sustained and fully integrated Polar observing system¹³.

3.1 Arctic observation questionnaire

To further understand the type of observational data that is being collected by the EU Polar Cluster and to identify the needs of Cluster projects we constructed a questionnaire and asked EU Polar Cluster members to respond to it. A selection of questions was developed and further refined at the Arctic PASSION GA in May 2022. We hosted a session of the EU Polar Cluster where we put these questions to around 20 individuals to gain feedback. The responses given were very helpful and have helped to shape the outcome of this deliverable. The questions that make up the questionnaire can be found in Appendix 1.

3.2 Additional information

Besides the Questionnaire mentioned above, two other forums were utilised. These were: (i) the EU Polar Cluster Booth and (ii) a dedicated EU Polar Cluster Session entitled: Coordination and networking for polar cooperation. Each forum is explained below.

¹² Link: <https://polarcatalyst.eu/>

¹³ White paper is here: <https://zenodo.org/records/10929817>

3.2.1. EU Polar Cluster Booth: 2024 Arctic Science Summit Week

The EU Polar Cluster organised a booth at the Arctic Science Summit Week (ASSW) in Edinburgh. The booth was organised and managed by members of Arctic PASSION, EU-PolarNet 2 and the European Polar Board. There were numerous materials from the EU Polar Cluster members to disseminate information. Additional information regarding the observational needs of EU Polar Cluster members were obtained from discussions at this booth.

EU Polar Cluster booth at ASSW 2024.
Photo credit Eva Horocakova EPB

3.2.2 EU Polar Cluster Session: Coordination and networking for polar cooperation

The EU Polar Cluster organised a formal session at ASSW on the 26th of March 2024. The aim of this event was to provide an opportunity for the EU Polar Clusters to network and exchange information between the participating projects.

Above: ASSW 2024 - EU Polar Cluster Session. Right, Arctic PASSION PI Michael Karcher.

Photo credit Eva Horocakova EPB

Several projects, like Arctic PASSION, shared their best practices regarding policy briefings. In addition, there was a moderated discussion about synergies between the different EU Polar Cluster members and observations. After this discussion the session continued with a presentation about working with stakeholders and rightsholders, as well as information for polar researchers about the different stakeholders and rightsholders. The Session concluded with a presentation about the scope for the integration of observations within the EU Polar Cluster and the need for a possible Observation Working Group within the Cluster. Following the

presentation was an open discussion about this subject and possible mechanisms to remedy it.

4. International organisations involved in coordinating Arctic observations

It is important to note that there are a tremendous number of diverse international organisations that are involved in Arctic observations, beyond those European initiatives listed in Section 2. Because of this complexity we only summarise several of the main organisations, as well as providing a link to their website should further information is needed. Note, this is not a comprehensive complete list.

- Arctic Council (AC): <https://arctic-council.org/>
- International Arctic Science Committee (IASC): <https://iasc.info/>
- Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS): <https://www.apecs.is/>
- World Meteorological Organization (WMO): <https://public.wmo.int/en>
- Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS): <https://gooscean.org/>
- Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks (SAON):
<https://arctic-council.org/projects/saon/>
 - Committee on Observations and Networks (CON):
<https://www.arcticobserving.org/committees/con/meetings>
 - Polar Observing Assets Working Group (POAWG):
<https://polarobservingregistry.org/poawg>
- International Arctic Buoy Program (IAPB): <https://iabp.apl.uw.edu/>
- ARGO initiatives such as: Euro Argo, Polar Argo: <https://argo.ucsd.edu/>
- Regional Distributed Biological Observatories (DBOs):
<https://arcticpassion.eu/adbo/>
- The Arctic Observing Summits (AOS): <https://arcticobservingsummit.org/>
- Arctic Science Ministerial (ASM1-3):
 - ASM1 (Washington):
<https://www.arctic.gov/arctic-science-ministerial-meeting/>
 - ASM2 (Berlin):
https://www.arcticscienceministerial.org/arctic/en/conference/conference-background/conference-background_node.html
 - ASM3 (Tokyo): <https://www.asm3.org/>

Whilst this is far from a comprehensive list, it is important to realise that new organisations are also being formed. For example, recently the international

community, via support from the G7 Future of Seas and Oceans Initiative¹⁴ (G7 FSOI), held discussions regarding the establishment of a comprehensive Arctic Ocean observing system, via an Arctic Ocean Regional Alliance (ARORA). Both the Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks¹⁵ (SAON) and the Global Ocean Observing System¹⁶ (GOOS) have agreed with the goal of designing and establishing a Global Regional Alliance¹⁷ (GRA) for the Arctic Ocean or similar structured organisation. An ARORA Task Team is presently being established and if successful ARORA will be a major player in Arctic Ocean observations. This highlights the importance of continued work in this area, and that the EU Polar Cluster can continue to have significant impact by working to find synergies with these wider networks and emerging groups.

It is worth noting that there are strong connections between Arctic PASSION and the above-mentioned European and International institutions with the EPB, SIOS, INTERACT, APECS, and SAON (via AMAP secretariat) being Partner organisations. Furthermore, several Partners of Arctic PASSION are also involved in EU-PolarNet 2 and other EU Polar Cluster projects, as well involvement in EuroGOOS, ARORA, ASM, AOS and G7 FSOI.

5. Summary and Recommendations

In this chapter we provide suggestions on how to address the three Challenges mentioned at the start of the report with respect to the EU Polar Cluster and the observations made by its Members¹⁸. To successfully address these challenges we need an EU Polar Cluster that is both relevant and sustainable. Therefore, this section also addresses the need to sustain the EU Polar Cluster over the medium to longer term.

Our results from the questionnaire (and other forums) suggest there is an appetite, and a strong requirement, for better coordination of Arctic observations within EU Polar Cluster programmes.

¹⁴ See <https://www.g7fsoi.org/>

¹⁵ See <https://www.arcticobserving.org/>

¹⁶ See <https://goosocean.org/>

¹⁷ See <https://goosocean.org/who-we-are/goos-regional-alliances/>

¹⁸ The three Challenges mentioned are:

- (i) better understand the observations that are (were) being performed within EU funded Arctic programmes;
- (ii) produce an accessible catalogue of meta-information of the EU Polar Cluster observations, contact points and information on when, where and how observational data are intended to be collected;
- (iii) provide opportunities to connect with individuals and organisations that can assist the observational measurements and logistic needs of EU Polar Cluster projects by creating a forum/process that enhances the exchange of information regarding each project's observational and logistical needs.

It would be an exceptional feat if this experience could be made available to all EU Polar Cluster members, as well as the Arctic observational community in general. One possible way is through establishing an accessible online EU Polar Cluster Observation Discussion Group/Hub.

Instigated by Arctic PASSION, the EU Polar Cluster have initiated and built an online Observations Group/Hub for better coordination of Arctic observations. This online forum is aimed to be used to (i) exchange experiences or advice on issues associated with observations, (ii) provide a mechanism to connect with people that can assist with a Cluster's observational or and logistical needs, (iii) provide a repository for protocols, procedures and best practice documents with respect to Arctic observations.

The online Observations Group/Hub is presently being tested on the EU Polar Cluster's Catalyst platform. It is following the same structure and format as the EU Polar Cluster's Stakeholder Tool that is also housed on the Catalyst platform. It will be an open forum that is searchable, structured along topics and have the possibility to pose questions to the community.

Screenshot of the EU Polar Cluster's Observations Group/Hub that is on the Catalyst platform.

The Observations Group/Hub is scheduled to go live to the EU Polar Cluster Members in Q4 2024. During the initial operation of the Observations Hub/Group each Cluster project should nominate one person to be the observational contact point. They can be the knowledgeable person in their project who can be the contact point for questions regarding the use of the Observations Group.

We believe the online Observations Group/Hub would provide a lasting legacy of observational knowledge from EU polar projects.

Recommendation #1: After appropriate testing, the EU Polar Cluster's online Observation Discussion Group/Hub should become operational. **Target:** EU Polar Cluster

Talking with the EU Polar Cluster members it is clear that there is a tremendous amount of experience in Arctic observations across all disciplines and biospheres. While the online Observation Discussion Group/Hub will provide an excellent forum for exchange of information, an overview on who is doing what in term of observations, methods, instruments, analysis tools etc, is still lacking. We thus recommend to put processes in place to collect the appropriate metrics (on observations) and then making these freely available. This could be achieved by developing a questionnaire/form that captures all the necessary information. Capturing this information could be a mandatory requirement for entry into the EU Polar Cluster. Furthermore, the questions could be drafted in such a way that the answers address the three challenges raised at the start of this report. These were to provide:

- i. better understand the observations that are (were) being performed within EU funded Arctic programmes;
- ii. produce an accessible catalogue of meta-information of the EU Polar Cluster observations, contact points and information on when, where and how observational data are intended to be collected;
- iii. provide opportunities to connect with individuals and organisations that can assist the observational measurements and logistic needs of EU Polar Cluster projects by creating a forum/process that enhances the exchange of information regarding each project's observational and logistical needs.

The availability of this information will obviously benefit the Cluster projects, but it could be passed on to the newly developed Polardex (see section 2.6.3) operational tool. By doing so the Arctic observations and infrastructure/logistics used by the EU Polar Cluster can be entered into Polardex; enhancing opportunities for all.

Recommendation #2: The EU Polar Cluster should develop a mandatory questionnaire for Members to complete that provides the necessary meta-information on the Arctic observations they will be performing. **Target:** EU Polar Cluster

Results from our information gathering exercises have shown that EU Polar Cluster projects collect observations right across the Arctic (presently excluding Russia, due to its illegal invasion of Ukraine), relating to a broad range of atmospheric, oceanic,

terrestrial, and cryospheric parameters, as well the those relating to ecosystems and those with a human dimension. A wide variety of platforms were utilised for the collection of these data, and involved meaningful partnerships with Indigenous People and Early Career Researchers, amongst others. Interestingly, a minority of observations made by Cluster were part of longer-term observational programmes, and about half were part of a National observational programme. It was unanimously agreed that the observations made by Cluster projects have a legacy that lives beyond the end of their programme. Almost all Cluster projects would like to develop links with the ESA Polar Science Cluster.

Recommendation #3: The EU Polar Cluster and ESA Polar Science Cluster should make greater efforts to foster closer ties in order to enhance Arctic observations, as well as to share resources and to co-develop opportunities, high-impact, strategic knowledge transfer events that showcase European Arctic science and its policy and societal implications. **Target:** European Commission, European Space Agency

5.1 Sustainably of the EU Polar Cluster

Whilst the Arctic region is currently facing a multitude of challenges, primarily driven by rapid environmental change, increased human-driven pressures and the heightened political tensions, European solidarity on Arctic research remains strong and integrated. Perhaps one of the reasons Europe has such a vibrant and dynamic Arctic research community is because of the existence of the EU Polar Cluster. The Cluster was established through the efforts of networking programmes such as the EU-PolarNet and its follow-on EU-PolarNet 2, as well as the proactive involvement of actors such as the European Polar Board, British Antarctic Survey, and the Svalbard Integrated Observing System. Through their hard work these and several other actors have instilled a positive, integrated and coherence to EU Arctic research. The eyes of the world are on the Arctic, and the actions of the EU Polar Cluster have not only promoted networking and collaborative research within Europe, but have enabled Europe Arctic science to be a key player in translating the many words spoken about the Arctic into actions and policies.

The EU Polar Cluster is the only body that represents EU funded Arctic projects, however the EU Polar Cluster is NOT on a sustainable footing. At present only 3 EU Polar Cluster projects out of more than 20 contribute to the running costs associated with the Cluster (in 2025 it will only be two projects contributing). The majority of the Cluster Members use the service free-of-charge. This obviously is not maintainable or desirable over the medium to long term.

Recommendation #4: Develop a sustainable funding framework for the EU Polar Cluster so that it is not reliant on only a few EU projects to cover all the running costs and commitments. **Target:** European Commission

Recommendation #5: The coordination of the EU Polar Cluster should be embedded within the structure of the newly formed European Polar Coordination Office. **Target:** EPB

5.2 Next Steps

We are fully aware that there is a lot of information within this report for the EU Polar Cluster to digest and potentially action regarding instigating an online group on observations in the EU Polar Cluster. We would suggest that at the next EU Polar Cluster Coordination Team meeting time is allocated to Arctic PASSION to present the results of this Deliverable. By doing so, the coordination team can quiz the authors of this report regarding the five recommendations and possible next steps. Furthermore, the issues and recommendations raised by this report could be discussed with the broader EU Polar Cluster membership at the next business meeting at the 2025 ASSW. The advantage of this is that the new EPB office in Sweden should be bedded in, and the associated EPCO office should have started.

Appendix 1 – Questionnaire

EU Polar Cluster - Observations Working Group

This questionnaire is to determine what areas each Cluster member, primarily the projects, are collecting observations in - geographically and type. The aim, long term, is to facilitate collaborations in obtaining measurements, deploying instrumentation, joining fieldwork, etc. to maximise impact and minimise resource requirements.

EU Polar Cluster - Observations Working Group

This questionnaire is to determine what areas each Cluster member, primarily the projects, are collecting observations in

- geographically and type. The aim, long term, is to facilitate collaborations in obtaining measurements, deploying instrumentation, joining fieldwork, etc. to maximise impact and minimise resource requirements.

NB this is alongside the Data Action Group - which covers areas around access of data once collected, so is out of scope here.

Inputs to this will initially go towards an Observations Hub on the Catalyst platform. This is initially a deliverable for Arctic PASSION, but is for the entire community. For long term use, answers will be made available to inform EPCO of the current collaborations - the EPB/EU-PolarNet 2 created the European Polar Coordination Office, that will be initiated in 2025. Please add any ideas or requirements that we should consider to better enable collaborations between projects and across other international initiatives.

General information

* Required

First name *

Surname *

email *

Institute *

Cluster member (project) *

Your role in the project

e.g. coordinator, WP leader on ##, task leader, comms/data contact, research specialist field

Metrics on observational data collected by EU Polar Cluster projects

Please answer on behalf of your full project where possible. We will combine results from more than one entry for a project.

What regions are your project performing your observations in?

- Arctic
- Antarctic
- Third Pole (mountainous regions)

What spheres are your project performing your observations in?

- Terrestrial
- Marine
- Atmosphere
- Cryosphere
- Social and Human

What platforms did/will your project use to collect data?

- Ship
- Aircraft
- Satellite (remote sensing)
- Terrestrial vehicles
- Autonomous platforms Human interactions

Is your project co-producing measurements with Indigenous communities?

- Yes
- No

Did/will Early Career Researchers take part in obtaining these measurements?

- Yes
- No

Do your measurements involve aspects of citizen science?

- Yes
- No

Will any of your observations continue beyond the end of the project?

If yes, please list under 'other'

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

Are your observations part of a long-term observational programme?

If yes, please list under 'other'

- Yes
- No
- Other

Are your observations part of a national programme?

If yes, please list under 'other'

- Yes
- No
- Other

Current linkages and collaborations for your project

We will add any pages or interactions that you add onto the Observation hub on the Catalyst platform. If you don't wish it to appear, please note this in the 'other' final question.

Do you have known links to ESA Polar Science Cluster projects? Please list/link

Would you like to link with ESA Polar Science Cluster projects?

- Yes
- No - already linked
- No - n/a
- Maybe

Is your project linked to SOOS? If so please describe how

Would you like to link with SOOS?

- Yes
- No - already linked
- No - n/a
- Maybe

Is your project linked to SAON? If so please describe how

Would you like to link with SAON?

- Yes
- No - already linked
- No - n/a
- Maybe

Is your project on POLARDEX?

- Yes - add link in 'other'
- No - n/a
- No - but would like to
- Other

Are there other international initiatives that you would like to mention?

If there are several answers for one initiative, we'll look to promoting

To create a forum within the EU Polar Cluster to exchange information

Did/will you contact/collaborated/ share data with other EU Polar Cluster projects?

- Yes, have done
- Yes, planning on
- No, not needed, n/a
- No, but would like to explore options

Would it be helpful to you to have advance knowledge of what observations other EU Polar Cluster programmes are performing?

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

Would you like to be part of an observational working group within the EU Polar Cluster?

- Yes
- No

Would you like Cluster Observations Group meetings with others planning observations?

We can provide discussion fora if appropriate, but don't want to add to overloaded calendars if engagement isn't wanted. If you do, please add frequency and topics to discuss. Please remember this is about collation of observational data, not about data processing or archiving.

How can we improve the sharing of observation plans and opportunities within the EU Polar Cluster?

Initial plans are to create a hub on the Catalyst platform. Further ideas can feed into the EPCO plans, once set up.

Is there anything else you'd like to add?

Appendix 2 – Graphic representation of Questionnaire results

Geographic region

Platforms used

Indigenous partnerships

Early Career Researchers

Legacy Observations

Member of long-term observations

Observations national programme

Share data with other EUCP

Part of EU Polar Cluster observational group

Link to ESA Polar Science cluster

